

Mapping the Future of AI in the Life Sciences

Insights from a National Consultation

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AI is altering what can be done in life-science

1. ChatGPT & friends are being utilized in much of the scientific process.

Writing

Coding/Analysis

Brainstorming

3. Prediction is a major driver for collecting molecular life-science data:

Disease risk & biomarkers

Understand and combining datasets

2. AlphaFold transformed Structural Biology, and impacting other areas.

Drug discovery

Synthetic Biology

Annotation

4. New AI capabilities are emerging rapidly, further changing what is possible

Novel discoveries

Improved productivity

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What do people mean by AI?

1. Prompt based systems

Send text to a text-based model, get an output or run a series of tools.

3. Problem-specific modelling

Training ML models for to understand your data/problem. But they are probably just for you

Predictive modelling

Multi-omics

2. AI powered bioinformatics tools

Software with AI under the hood - user needs to know how to run/interpret but not how the AI works

4. Novel AI methods

Build AI models to develop a new method/technique, ideally for others. Often requires big data & compute.

New AI models

Australian BioCommons enables the analysis of omics data through providing national digital research infrastructure

Undertake extensive **community engagement** to identify gaps

Develops and maintains **community scale digital infrastructure** with a network of NCRIS and other partners

Streamlines **access to national scale analysis and data services**

Delivers a national bioinformatics **training program**

- Galaxy Australia
- Australian Apollo Service
- Australian AlphaFold Service
- Australian Fgenesh++ Service
- Australian Nextflow Seqera Service
- Australian BioCommons Leadership Share
- Bioinformatics Tool and Workflow Finders
- Training Infrastructure as a Service

Offers national scale strategic **advice and leadership**

Collaborates internationally to achieve these goals

Infrastructure: all components that enable access

User Knowledge & Skills
Users have to know these tools exist and how to use them

Software and workflows
How to run AI tools on my data & compute within workflows that make sense for me

Hardware
The right mix of GPUs and storage

Data
Access to reference datasets, standards for sharing, secure environments for sensitive data

Expertise
people who can guide researchers and troubleshoot challenges

Access and governance
ethics, data sharing agreements, security for clinical data

BioCommons is already responding to AI

Australian AlphaFold Service

- AF2 predicts a protein's structure from its sequence
- Available for use via Galaxy Australia, which provides the underlying compute power and set up needed to run AlphaFold
- More than 30,000 jobs run to date
- Fully subsidised for Australian researchers
- Register for access via Galaxy Australia

Click + drag to rotate the structure

CTRL + click + drag to move the structure

Scroll up/down to zoom in and out

AlphaFold produces a per-residue confidence score (pLDDT) between 0 and 100. Some regions below 50 pLDDT may be unstructured in isolation.

www.biocommons.org.au/services

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Outreach to establish community needs

“User-centric design must lie at the heart of Australia's NDRI system”

**AI Roundtable,
Melbourne 2025**

National AI Survey

**Focus Groups
on AI Training**

... plus 50+ informal consultation across Australia's life science community.

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A Collaborative Path to AI Literacy

Our purpose is to build researcher confidence and capability by delivering an **inclusive**, and **community informed framework** for integrating AI into life science research.

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Focus Group Methodology

Design Think Make Break Repeat

- **Make:** Participants ideate a "Magic AI Assistant" to define the maximum theoretical utility of AI in life science workflows.
- **Break:** Identified current barriers and systemic blockers to isolate the constraints.
- **Repeat:** Researchers co-designed the training roadmap, ensuring that it is optimised for domain relevance and uptake.

Focus Group Methodology

Aim: To identify researcher needs and barriers to design a tailored AI in life science research training program.

Structure

- 60 min Zoom sessions
- 3 – 5 participants per session with 2 facilitators
- Total of 19 participants across 5 focus groups

If you had a “Magic AI Assistant” that could do one repetitive task for you today, what would that task be?

If you had a 'Magic AI Assistant' that could do one repetitive research task for you today, what would that task be?

✦ 7 groups found

Literature Review

10 responses

"Literature review", "making paper summary for lit r..."

Data Analysis

8 responses

"Cancer data analysis", "Help with Data Analysis T..."

Coding

4 responses

"Coding", "fast coding", "genome annotation"

Reference Management

4 responses

"Reference formatting/checking in manuscripts", "..."

✦ Press **SPACE** to hide groups

→ End presentation

34 / 50

If you had a 'Magic AI Assistant' that could do one repetitive research task for you today, what would that task be?

✦ 7 groups found

Grant Applications

3 responses

"Apply for grants", "Grants", "Aligning grants to requ..."

Workflow Automation

3 responses

"Build agent to create and run workflow", "Help m..."

New responses

Uncategorized

8 responses

"Already use for simple coding but more ambitious..."

✦ Press **SPACE** to hide groups

→ End presentation

34 / 50

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Uncategorized

8 responses

Already use for simple coding but more ambitious coding like making a package

Respond to emails

code troubleshooting

I would want it to help me design experiments and interpret data.

Curate and download datasets of interest

DESIGN COMPOUND

Attend meetings so I can actually do work

keywords and search strings

✦ Press **SPACE** to hide groups

→ End presentation

34 / 50

What are survey and focus group results?

What questions did we want to answer

1. Who is using AI, what are they using it for? What are their challenges?
2. What are the compute challenges that people run into (GPU? Storage? Access?)
3. What skills do people want? How should we deliver training/support?

Researcher Profiles: Current Role

Expectation: Mostly PhD

Reality: Mostly research support staff!

Researcher Profiles: Research Domain

Survey are mostly human genetics (red) and then a broad mix.
Focus groups were microbiome and genomics

Most survey responders are ML experts

Expectation:

We think most life-scientists are not building ML models **but expect** survey will over-represent AI experts.

Results: 53% of responders are building ML models in some way (applied ML or AI developers).

Are you building AI/ML models?

Current experiences with using AI tools

How would you describe your current interaction with AI/ML your research practice? Select all that apply (n=59)

- People are using LLM/Agents a lot, particularly coding, explanation and literature synthesis
- Users vary in terms of degree and domains where they are skeptical of outputs
- Split in dealing with hallucinations.
 - Some distrust the outputs
 - Some provide models with resources to try produce reliable answers.

“

“I wanted to update some code...thought I'll get AI to help me make the change...in the end, it did **help**...but it was **frustrating** the extent to which I had to **oversee** what was done”

People are running a diverse mix of tools

What AI bioinformatics tools are you using? (n=50) Lots of protein structure and design related tools.

“Others” reflects many domains each with their own tools/challenges including:

- Candidate CRISPR selection (*CRISPick*)
- Microscopy analysis (*imaging models*)
- Rat pose modelling (*DeepLabCut*)
- Deploying AI models locally (*Ollama/LMStudio*)

Storage and data movement is a major challenge

What are your computational bottlenecks? (n=48)

If you have them, what would help your storage or data management needs? (n=48)

What are adoption barriers? Time + many things

- #1 barrier is time
 - Catch all for not knowing how to integrate AI with all existing ways of working
- Unclear data privacy rules
 - What is sensitive data or not?
- Access to models/tools
 - I personally pay for a tool I use for work
 - *"I'm stuck using CoPilot but I know Claude is better"*
 - Its not clear if I'm allowed to use ChatGPT
- Speed of change:
 - *"I don't know what AI can practically do for me"*

“

“You know, new things are coming out all the time around privacy and regulations, so the **rate of change** just makes every aspect more **challenging.**”

“

“You try the bicycle, and you're saying it doesn't go as fast as a car, right?...I mean, I'm gonna keep **paying out of pocket**, because it's [AI tool] obviously worth it”

AI Training Program Design

To overcome time constraints, researchers prefer:

- Live workshops
- Research domain specific examples
- Drop-in sessions where they can get expert help on their unique projects

“

“I would say that on-demand resources are more efficient, but I don't use them. Whereas if it's something that is...a live workshop...I've forced myself to **dedicate time** to, then I'm more likely to actually do it”

What did we learn?

1. Who is using AI, what are they using it for? What are their challenges?

- (Almost) everyone in some way - majority are ChatGPT for admin and coding
 - ..but still many people want to build “classical machine learning” models
- Different domains need different tools for their distinct challenges

What are their challenges?

- Access to models and compute is not enough - skills, equity and clear policy are super important.

2. What are the compute challenges that people run into (GPU? Storage? Access?)

- GPUs are a problem but storage and memory are also big issues.

3. What skills do people want? How should we deliver training/support?

- People want in-person training on a diverse set of topics
- There is a segment that want advise from experts

Mapping the Path for AI in Life Sciences

Some early thoughts and ideas...

FOUNDATIONAL SKILLS

Live workshops to block out dedicated time for learning how to identify "LLM-shaped" tasks.

DOMAIN SPECIFIC MODULES

Move beyond generic prompts to targeted modules featuring relevant life science examples

TAILORED SUPPORT

Drop-in sessions for expert troubleshooting of unique research workflows

What's Next?

- **Generative AI Essentials for Life Sciences**
 - AI tool selection, ethics, navigating policy and prompting
- **Australian AI in Life Science Landscape Document:**
 - Consolidating all learnings in one place
 - Public draft coming soon for community input.
- Join the **AI in Molecular Life Science** conversation.
- **AI Community Survey** is still open
 - Please complete and/or share with your network
 - Would love to hear more students and ECRs.

WORKSHOP

Generative AI Essentials for Life Sciences

Dr Angus Fisk
Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney

Dr Minh Huynh
Australian BioCommons & Sydney Informatics Hub

Tell us what you thought ...

Feedback survey

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WORKSHOP

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